
Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Nigeria National Health Insurance Scheme in Ameliorating the Huge Medical Bills and Out of Pocket Expenditure of Its Enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre. Calabar Cross River State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effectiveness and efficiency of National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) on the amelioration of enrollees' huge medical bills and out-of-pocket expenditures at the University of Calabar Medical Centre. One null hypothesis and one research question were formulated each in line with the objective of the study. The study reviewed few related literature on NHIS and other public health intervention programmes. The Health Services Utilization Model by Ronald Max Andersen in 1968 and Welfaric theory by Vilfredo Pareto & co in 1978 were adopted respectively to adumbrate the phenomenon under evaluation. Survey research designed and inferential statistics were used for the methodology through the use of SPSS version 27.0.1. The study employed both quantitative and qualitative data analysis technique as primary and secondary data were used. The study population was made-up of the 800 principal enrollees of NHIS at the University of Calabar Medical Centre. The sample size (266) was determined by Taro Yamane formula even though only 252 questionnaires were later retrieved. The result of the findings revealed that there is no significant reduction or amelioration of huge medical bills on NHIS enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre hence the Correlation Coefficient (r) was -.063 and the p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) was .374 which was greater than the typical significant level of 0.05. The study recommended that; NHIA should henceforth do a policy adjustment to grant regular laboratory test services, supplies of drugs and other ancillary medical services to ensure that it aligns with the enrollees' medical needs because there was no direct correlation between the two variables.

KEYWORDS: Huge Medical Bills, Healthcare, National Health Insurance Scheme, Unical

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INTRODUCTION

Generally across the globe health insurance programmes like the Nigeria National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) are government social health-security programmes that are always enacted with the view of enhancing and improving the socio-economic, physical, and mental well-being of citizens. Public health intervention policies like the NHIS are often run by gazetted government health agencies as well as nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), that their activities and goals are related to the provision of medical healthcare services, food and water supply promotion activities etc.

Ideally, healthcare service provision by government entities to citizens or workers as it relates to this study, do varies from one nation to another, where their individual patterns of policy formulation and implementation mechanism do differ from each other respectively (Alagbor, et al. 2025). In contemporary days, healthcare service delivery that leads to workers welfare and citizens has become a fundamental tool to the development of the society at large, that was why, the World Health Organization (2012)

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developed a Universal Health Promotion Mechanism known as Universal Health Insurance Coverage (UHC) to mitigate short life expectancy that is often occasioned by inadequate healthcare service delivery in the society (Sekhri, & Savedoff, 2004). According to Adeniji, (2017), the prevailing circumstances that led to this beautiful societal health policy was designed to provide citizens with full range access to quality healthcare services delivery, where it will be provided to them without financial burden. Healthcare provision is the promotion of good healthcare services delivery such as prevention, treatment, rehabilitation and palliative cares across lives hence, the delivery of this services requires government human and financial resources which must be equitably distributed across board. Unarguably, public health intervention programmes are often targeted at protecting citizens from financial burdens and consequential stress of paying so much on healthcare services out of their own pockets thereby protecting them from poverty because unexpected illness do requires them to use their life saving assets or borrowings to curb such ailment (Alagbor, et al. 2025). This therefore justifies WHO recommendation in 2012 that gave countries with fragile healthcare systems like Nigeria and other third world countries the impetuosity to formulate healthcare policies and programmes that can deliver the goals of Universal Health Coverage (UHC).

Universally, medical welfare is usually a health-security policy and programme that is normally designed to support citizens or workers well-being. Medical Welfarism, as it is commonly known in socio-political sphere; it is a kind of government support initiative that is always intended to ensure that members of the society meets basic human medical needs. This is where the redistributive form of policy model normally comes into play. Furthermore; workers medical welfare through amelioration of huge medicals is a human resource management technique that is always programmed to address employee's dissatisfactions and improve on their morale and productivity, it often prevents staff from running away from organizational responsibilities hence they will be protected from hazards and enhance organizational productivity (Alagbor et al. 2025). According to International Labour Organization (2014), social welfare is best defined by providing medical security support to workers or citizens such as medical service delivery, sick leave, as well as disability benefits and occupational injuries.

The Nigeria National Health Insurance Scheme now managed by National Health Insurance Authority (NHIA) is a social-health insurance programme that was introduced in 2004 after Ghana had introduced her own programme in 2003 to ensure a universal access to good healthcare services for her citizens, by protecting individuals and families from financial burdens to healthcare service and ensuring availability of funds to health sector to improve services delivery to humanity (Sarpong & Fobil, 2018). From the statutory mandate of NHIS, as currently managed by the National Health Insurance Authority, the country's Health Insurance Scheme is supposed to be a very sustainable healthcare financing mechanism where the beneficiaries of the programme like the University of Calabar workers can enjoy it.

The scope of this study was strictly concerned with the evaluation of the effectiveness of National Health Insurance Scheme and the amelioration of huge medical bills for its enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre from the period of 2003 to 2026. The study was anchored on two theoretical frame work namely; Health Services Utilization Model by Ronald Max Andersen in 1968 and welfaric theory by Vilfredo Pareto & co in 1978. Under the significance of the study, the outcome of this study will be of great importance to: the government of Nigeria, the University of Calabar hence the responses from the enrollees will help the University to ascertain if the medical bills of the enrollees have actually been reduced by NHIS or not, the study will form part of public health literature, the outcome of the study shall also be of great significance to World Health Organization.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Statutorily, The vision and mandate of the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), was designed to ameliorate the huge medical bills of citizens and workers of public service in Nigeria but 22 years after its promulgation, one can be tempted to draw an inference that; the policy goals and vision seems to have very insignificant achievement hence empirical findings have shown that, Nigeria workers or citizens such as the University of Calabar workers or staff are not really enjoying the beautiful plans of the scheme as workers and citizens often complains of the challenges of paying so much on medical bills, perceived corruption from collaborative agencies like health management organization (HMO), the challenges with which the enrollees are often confronted with during reimbursement and authorization code amongst other dilemmas has imposed significant challenges on the success of the scheme. It is against this backdrop and unclear achievements of NHIS that; the researchers took the bull by its horns to investigate this statutory objective of the scheme (exemption of enrollees from huge medical bills) and ascertain whether it has impacted positively on the medical welfare of the University of Calabar workers or not because in spite of its establishment over 22 years ago, the financial burdens of enrollees households seems to have continued to rise astronomically, especially that a recent survey estimate has proven that over 91% of Nigerians who are enrollees with NHIS still finances their healthcare through out-of-pocket (OPP) expenditures, (Alagbor, et al. 2025).

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RESEARCH QUESTION

The understated research question for this study was formulated to drive home a successful evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of NHIA.

- To what extent has National Health Insurance Scheme ameliorated huge medical bills and out-of-pocket expenditures for its enrollees at University of Calabar Medical Centre.

OBJECTIVE OF THE` STUDY

- To evaluate the extent to which NHIS has ameliorated or reduced huge medical bills and out-of-pocket expenditures for its enrollees at University of Calabar Medical Centre.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- There is no significant relationship between the amelioration of huge medical bills by NHIS on its enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre.

LITERATURE REVIEW

All over the world, World Health Organization (WHO) has been encouraging countries across the globe to keep providing less expensive healthcare services to their citizens and in doing so it has been providing free drugs and vaccines to certain groups of people in the society like children, people with disabilities, old peoples and other vulnerable groups etc. Alagbor, et al. (2025), confirmed that for any country to grow economically, such a country must provide adequate funding for healthcare services, bearing in mind that the end product is to accomplish the expected levels of healthcare status and economic improvement. The journey to achieve the current Nigeria national health insurance scheme could be trace back to the era of Dr. Moses Majekodunmi efforts in 1962 when he was the Minister for Health. Agba (2010), opined that Dr. Majekodunmi initiated this idea to address the medical welfare of Nigeria public sector workers with the view of attaining high level of National productivity. Unfortunately, the attempted break-up of country in the year 1967 to 1970 (Civil War) stroked on the scheme and it was halted, but in the year 1984, the Military regime of General Buhari revived the scheme again and set up a committee led by Late Prof. Olikoye Ransome Kutyi. In 1988 the committee was inaugurated to comprehensively review the objective of the scheme as the committee later submitted the report to Federal Executive Council in 1989 (Agba 2010). Adesina (2009) reported that; immediately after the findings of ILO and UNDP, the Federal Military Government of Nigeria in 1993 later gave a matching order to the Federal Ministry of Health to kick-start NHIS officially in Nigeria and the NHIS was promptly put to action. In May, 1999 the need for a constitutionally established NHIS was adopted and enshrined in the 1999 Constitution as the 2004 Act of National Assembly was later enacted to explicitly define the statutory responsibilities of the scheme and the Act was implemented in 2005.

The exemption of Nigeria workers or enrollees from huge medical bills by NHIS is a statutory responsibility of the agency which means that; the institutionalization of the policy from the onset was to provide direct medical healthcare service protection on their enrollees. Alagbor, et al. (2025), assessed the impact of NHIS on medical welfare of University of Calabar workers and the findings of the study revealed that a great number of the University of Calabar Medical Centre enrollees with NHIS are still paying huge on drugs and laboratory test services for their medication as the empirical investigation further affirmed that some enrollees can't even save money for other physiological needs. Mesah (2010) confirmed that the rate of catastrophic expenditures on health care as a result of out-of-pocket (OOP) method is too much in Nigeria. Similarly, Onoka et al. (2013). Highlighted the constraints of scaling up the coverage of NHIS including limited financial resources amongst enrollees is another setback. Alawode, & Adewole, (2021). Assessed the implementation challenges of the National Health Insurance Scheme at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital and the result of study opined that health insurance is an important mechanism to preventing financial hardship in the process of accessing health care but a reverse seems to be the case with NHIS, Nigeria. The study further revealed that since the launch of Nigeria's National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) in 2005, only 5% of Nigerians have got health insurance and 70% still finances their healthcare through Out-Of-Pocket (OOP) expenditure.

Alagbor, et al. (2025), also opined that everywhere in the world, sufficient provision of drugs to beneficiaries under public health intervention programmes like NHIS often leads to proper medical welfare for the people, that was why the Nigeria national health insurance scheme (NHIS) in its wisdom adopted healthcare service delivery via the provision of drugs as one of its major objectives. But several years after the inauguration of the scheme, there seems to be no significant achievement of the scheme by significantly ameliorating out-of-pocket expenditures on enrollees. Yusuf & Akinmola (2019). Investigated NHIS's impact on healthcare delivery and cost implication amongst beneficiaries of the scheme in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital and the findings revealed a very weak or insignificant relationship between NHIS and quality of healthcare on the beneficiaries.

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THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

The study adopted two theoretical frame works namely; Health Services Utilization Model by Ronald Max Andersen in 1968 and the Welfaric Theory propounded by Vilfredo Pareto, Alfred Marshall and Arthur C. Pigou in the year 1897. The study would have been adumbrated by several other theories, but the study saw these two theories as the most appropriate that can explain the phenomena under evaluation with closely related characteristics and justifications. The Ronald M. Andersen’s Health Services Utilization Model argued that; healthcare access and utilization are always influenced by individuals and contextual factors or laws. The renowned American health services theorist adumbrated that the use of healthcare services is usually a function of predisposing factors, such as demographics and social structure. The framework further highlighted the complex interplay between individuals and environmental factors as well as income and insurance laws that normally shapes healthcare service policies and utilization patterns across the world which can impliedly infer to Nigeria NHIS according to the healthcare policy mandate.

The welfaric theory propounded by Vilfredo Pareto and co. in the 19th century argued that; all government actions and inactions are supposed to be taken in a manner that must achieve the socio-economic, medical wellbeing and security of the people which is fundamental to the interpretation of this study variables (Alagbor et al. 2025). In the lenses and the perspective of the neoclassical economist (Vilfredo Pareto) “man earns money to pay for his food, physiological needs and medical welfare, just as government spends money to develop policies and programmes for the welfare of the people and workers. The Paretian theorist further argued that the principle of welfaric economy is always derived from a legitimate improvement strategy, which occurs when a particular socio-economic policy of government makes a greater number of people happier and not like the perceived case of national health insurance scheme policy where there seems to be no significant betterment for the enrollees because each individual is the best judge of his or her own welfare.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed survey research design and made use of both inferential and descriptive statistics hence data were generate via multistage sampling technique. The population of the study covered only the staff of the University of Calabar who are the principal enrollees with NHIS at Unical Medical Centre with a total population of eight hundred people (800). The Taro Yamane formula was used in determining the sample size which was 266 respondents representing 0.352% of the population though at end of data collection exercise only 255 questionnaires were retrieved from respondents. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistical tool was deployed for analysis of the test of hypothesis through the use of SPSS version 27.0.1

DATA PRESENTATION

Table 1: Enrollees could save more money and buy properties because of reduced medical bills and out-of-pocket expenditure introduced by NHIS?

S/N		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
1	Strongly Agreed	89	34.9	34.9	34.9
2	Agreed	79	30.9	30.9	65.8
3	Undecided	2	0.8	0.8	66.6
4	Disagree	30	11.8	11.8	78.4
5	Strongly Disagree	55	21.6	21.6	100
6	Total	255	100		

Source: Field Work, 2026

Table 1 data shows that 89 respondents constituting 34.9% strongly agreed that NHIS enrollees at Uncial Medical Centre do experience out-of-pocket expenditures hence prescribe drugs and other medical services are not always available. 79 (30.9%) respondents also agreed to the assertion, and 2 (.08%) respondents were undecided. whereas, 30 respondents representing 11.8% disagreed to the assertion, and 55 (21.6%) respondents strongly disagree. In the light of the above, majority of the respondents strongly agreed that NHIS enrollees at Uncial Medical Centre do experience serious out-of-pocket expenditures cumulating to huge medical bills hence prescribe drugs and other medical services are not always available whereas a few percentage of the respondents disagreed on the item.

Table 2: Enrollees can now support community development activities as a result of reliefs from huge medical bills by NHIS?

S/N		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
1	Strongly Agreed	24	9.4	9.4	9.4

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2	Agreed	38	14.9	14.9	24.3
3	Undecided	6	2.4	2.4	26.7
4	Disagree	86	33.7	33.7	60.4
5	Strongly Disagree	101	39.6	39.6	100
6	Total	255	100		

Source: Field Work, 2026

Table 2 revealed that 24 respondents constituting 9.4% strongly agreed that NHIS enrollees can now support community development programmes hence their reduced medical bills by NHIS. 38 (14.9%) respondents also agreed to the assertion, and 6 (2.4%) respondents were undecided. Meanwhile, 86 respondents representing 33.7% disagreed with the assertion, and 101 (39.6%) respondents strongly disagreed to the assertion. Base on the foregoing numeric analysis, majority of the respondents strongly disagreed that NHIS enrollees can now support community development programmes because of their ameliorated medical bills by NHIS whereas only a few insignificant percentage agree on the item.

Table 3: Enrollees currently attends to more domestic needs through extra income saved from reduced medical bills by NHIS?

S/N		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
1	Strongly Agreed	22	8.6	8.6	8.6
2	Agreed	19	7.5	7.5	16.1
3	Undecided	8	3.1	3.1	19.2
4	Disagree	94	36.9	36.9	56.1
5	Strongly Disagree	112	43.9	43.9	100
6	Total	255	100		

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 3 confirmed that 22 respondents constituting 8.6% strongly agreed that enrollees currently attends to more domestic needs through extra income saved from reduced medical bills by NHIS, 38 (14.9%) respondents agreed on the assertion, and 8 (3.1%) respondents were undecided. Meanwhile, 94 respondents representing 36.9% disagreed that; enrollees currently attends to more domestic needs through extra income saved from reduced medical bills by NHIS and 112 (43.9%) respondents strongly disagreed. Consequently, from the foregoing analysis, majority of the respondents strongly disagreed that; enrollees currently attends to more domestic needs because of reduced medical bills by NHIS whereas a very insignificant percentage of respondents agree to the view.

Table 4: Enrollees could meet children’ school fees now easily hence the reduced medical bills or out-of-pocket expenditure by NHIS?

S/N		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Agreed	38	14.9	14.9	14.9
2	Agreed	41	16.1	16.1	31
3	Undecided	1	0.4	0.4	31.4
4	Disagree	98	38.4	38.4	69.8
5	Strongly Disagree	77	30.2	30.2	100
6	Total	255	100		

Source: Field Work, 2026

Table 4 indicates that 38 respondents representing 14.9% strongly agreed that enrollees could meet-up with children’ school fees now because of reduced medical bills or out-of-pocket expenditure by NHIS, 41 (16.1%) respondents agreed, and 1 (0.4%) respondents stood on undecided. Whereas, 98 respondents representing 38.4% disagreed with the assertion and 77 (30.2%) respondents strongly disagreed. Base on the foregoing tabular analysis, majority of the respondents disagreed that NHIS have brought about the reduction in out-of-pocket expenditures or bills amongst enrollees in Unical Medical Centre wherefore the scheme could be termed ineffective and discouraging to enrollees.

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Table 5: Dependent Variable; your overall experience with NHIS has improved since you got enrolled at Unical Medical Centre.

S/N		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
1	Strongly Agreed	13	5.1	51.	5.1
2	Agreed	24	9.4	9.4	14.5
3	Undecided	1	0.4	0.4	14.9
4	Disagree	99	38.8	38.8	53.7
5	Strongly Disagree	118	46.3	46.3	100
6	Total	255	100		

Source: Field Work, 2026

Table 5 attest that 13 respondents representing 5.1% strongly agreed that, the overall health conditions of enrollees has improved since they got enrolled with NHIS at Unical Medical Centre, 24 (9.4%) respondents agreed, and 1 (0.4%) respondents were undecided. Whereas, 99 respondents representing 38.8% disagreed with the assertion and 118 (46.3%) respondents strongly disagreed. Therefore from the data presented and analyzed, majority of the respondents strongly disagreed that the overall health condition of enrollees has improved since they got enrolled with NHIS at Unical Medical Centre. Thus; the scheme could be term discouraging to enrollees and the intending ones.

Test of Hypothesis			
Table 6			
EFFECT_NHIS	Pearson Correlation	1	-.063
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.374
	N	255	252
HUGE_MEDBIL	Pearson Correlation	-.063	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.374	
	N	252	252

Source: Pearson product moment correlation tool, 2026

Table 6 confirmed that Pearson product-moment correlation analysis between the two variables (effectiveness of NHIS and the amelioration of huge medical bills), where the Correlation Coefficient (r) was -.063, indicating a very weak and negative correlation or effect between effectiveness of NHIS and amelioration of huge medical bills of NHIS enrollees with the University of Calabar Medical Centre. Under the significance; the p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) is .374, which was greater than the typical significance level of 0.05 which means that the correlation was not statistically significant hence the sample size (N) was 252. Based on this result, it is right to state that the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the amelioration of huge medical bills by NHIS on its enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre was retained.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The amelioration of huge medical bills or Out-of-Pocket expenditures of enrollees by NHIS is a statutory responsibility of the scheme but the results of this study shows that, there is a gross ineffectiveness and inefficiency on the part of NHIS hence the result of findings from data presented, analyzed and test of hypothesis shows that there is no significant relationship between the effectiveness of NHIS and the amelioration of enrollees medical bills at the University of Calabar Medical Centre. The findings from the results also indicates that there is a very weak correlation coefficient (r) between the two variables (effectiveness of NHIS on the amelioration of enrollees’ medical bills) which impliedly infers that, the null hypothesis was retained. Thus; the result of this hypothesis is in-tandem with the work of Yusuf & Akinmola (2019), who investigated the effectiveness of NHIS and healthcare delivery in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital. Similarly, the result of this study also agrees with the work of Alagbor et al. (2025) who assessed the impact of NHIS on the medical welfare of University of Calabar staff. In the same vein the result of this study also agrees with the earlier work of Alawode & Adewole (2021), who identified design and implementation challenges amongst actors and enrollees in selected sub-national levels public health centres in Nigeria, including inadequate capitation fees and poor awareness among enrollees. The result of this study also agrees with the work of Sarpong & Fobil (2018), evaluated the impact of Ghana national health insurance coverage on socio-economic health of citizens in a rural districts of Ghana

CONCLUSION

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This study undertook a mix-method and longitudinal research evaluation on the effectiveness of National Health Insurance Scheme and the amelioration of huge medical bills of enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre. From the result of the research exercise, it was concluded that; there is no significant relationship between the effectiveness of NHIS on the reduction of huge medical bills of enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre hence the correlation coefficient (r) was very weak (-0.063) and the statistical value (p-value=0.374) was greater than the typical significant level of 0.05 as well as their Out-of-Pocket (OOP) expenditures. To this end, the study finally concluded that; the National Health Insurance Scheme now managed by National Health Insurance Authority hasn't ameliorated or reduced the huge medical bills or Out-of-Pocket Expenditures of its enrollees at the University of Calabar Medical Centre thereby leading to poor healthcare service delivery from the agency, hence the empirical studies of other authors agreed with the study's findings through the instrument of hypothesis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study therefore recommends that, for NHIS to ameliorate the out-of-pocket expenditures or huge medical bill on its enrollees the agency must henceforth make available the necessary healthcare service provision mechanisms like laboratory test services, prompt supplies of drugs and other medical equipment by health management organizations (HMOs). The study also recommended that the agency's activities should henceforth be strictly monitored by the Federal Government of Nigeria in collaboration with their benefiting institutions particularly, the University of Calabar. The study further recommended that, the National Assembly House Committee on health should henceforth be monitoring and evaluating the policies of NHIA to enhance effective and efficient health care service delivery to the enrollees because during the process of data collection and analysis, almost 95% of the respondents decried how they often spends so much on medications such as prescribed drugs and laboratory tests services via out-of-pocket (OOP) expenditures. NHIA as an implementing agency should henceforth develop a policy adjustment on drugs provision and laboratory services to align with the enrollees' medical needs because there was a very weak correlation between the two major variables of the study.

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